
Submuscular locked compression plating and elastic stable intramedullary nailing for children with diaphyseal fractures of femur: An open labelled randomized controlled trial

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Abstract:

Objectives: To conduct a comparative evaluation of submuscular locked compression plating (SLCP, intervention) and elastic stable intramedullary nailing (ESIN, control) among children 5 to 15 years of age with diaphyseal fractures of femur. **Methods:** This was a hospital based open labelled randomized controlled trial conducted among children presenting with diaphyseal fractures of femur in the Department of Pediatric Orthopedics of a tertiary healthcare facility in south India between January 2018 and December 2018. **Results:** The present study included a total of 60 children – 30 children were treated with SLCP and the other 30 were treated with ESIN. None of the patients in either the intervention or the control arm developed malunion, deep surgical wound infections, or nerve injuries or compartment syndrome. 10.0% patients had loss of reduction post-surgery due to trivial fall requiring closed reduction, and 16.7% reported joint stiffness in the ESIN (control) arm. The mean (SD) global function scores in PODCI scale and subscale scores (upper extremity and physical function, transfers and basic mobility, sports and physical function, pain and comfort) among patients in the intervention arm was significantly higher than that reported among patients in the control arm. Though the happiness scores were significantly higher among patients in the intervention arm ($p < 0.05$), no significant difference between intervention and control arms was found in terms of expectations ($p > 0.05$). Duration of hospital stay, time taken for union, and blood loss (in ml) did not vary significantly between the study groups ($p > 0.05$). However, the duration of radiation required was significantly shorter among patients in the intervention arm in comparison with the control arm. **Conclusion:** While both SLCP and ESIN are viable treatment options for diaphyseal femur fractures in children, SLCP appears to offer distinct advantages in terms of functional outcomes and patient happiness. Moreover, the reduced radiation exposure associated with SLCP is a notable benefit.

Keywords: Diaphyseal femur fractures, Children, Pediatric orthopedics, India, randomized controlled trial, Functional outcomes.

Introduction

Diaphyseal femur fractures in children represent a significant orthopedic challenge, often necessitating surgical intervention to ensure optimal recovery and long-term functional outcomes.(1) These fractures, while relatively infrequent (accounts for 1.7% of all pediatric fractures with an annual incidence of 19 per 100,000 children),(2) require careful consideration of various surgical techniques to address the unique anatomical and biomechanical characteristics of pediatric bone.(3) Fracture management is affected by associated injuries, patient age, fracture characteristics, body weight, and cost.(4) During the past decade, surgical stabilization has gained favor in the management of femoral shaft fractures in skeletally immature patients.(5) Options for surgical stabilization include open or submuscular plate fixation, flexible intramedullary nailing, and rigid intramedullary nailing.(6) Each method has advantages and disadvantages, with the ideal technique largely debated.

Submuscular plating is an established operative treatment for femur fractures, acting as an internal splint, providing stable fixation, and allowing for maximum biologic healing.(7) Alternatively, flexible intramedullary nailing has become a popular method of treatment, with good clinical outcomes and low complication rates.(8) However, recent studies showed an increased risk of complications when flexible nails are used in heavier children and those with fractures of unstable length.(9-11) Femoral shaft fractures treated with rigid antegrade intramedullary nailing have shown promising results, but this treatment is generally reserved for older children and adolescents.(12) This technique affords stable internal fixation and allows for early mobilization. Previously, a piriformis entry point was used, but this technique has been associated with avascular necrosis of the femoral head. Trochanteric entry has reduced the risk of avascular necrosis, with only two reported cases.(13, 14) In this context, the choice of the most appropriate treatment modality becomes a critical decision, impacting not only immediate postoperative outcomes but also the quality of life and functional capacity of the young patients throughout their growth and development.

Against this background, we aim to address critical questions surrounding the management of diaphyseal femur fractures in children, with a focus on the comparative evaluation of submuscular locked compression plating (intervention) and elastic stable intramedullary nailing (control). Through an evidence-based analysis of clinical, functional, and patient-reported outcomes, we endeavor to provide valuable insights to guide orthopedic practitioners in their treatment decisions for this unique patient group.

Materials and methods

This was a hospital based open labelled randomized controlled trial conducted among children presenting with diaphyseal fractures of femur in the Department of Pediatric Orthopedics of a tertiary healthcare facility in south India between January 2018 and December 2018. The study was approved by the Institutional Human Ethics Committee (IHEC). The content of Participant Information Sheet (PIS) in local language was provided to the participants (and their attenders) and contents were read to them in their own language to their satisfaction. The participants were enrolled in the study after obtaining written informed consent. The present study included children 5 to 15 years of age presenting to the Department of Pediatric Orthopedics with diaphyseal fractures of femur (that is, the upper limit starting below lesser trochanter and distal limit decided by Muller square). However, previously operated cases, other or additional injuries that will interfere with patient rehabilitation, patients presenting with head injuries, Glasgow Coma scale scores less than 11, pathological fractures and open fractures were excluded.

The intervention or experimental arm of the trial received submuscular locked compression plating (SLCP) and the patients in the control group received elastic stable intramedullary nailing (ESIN). We computed sample size as two proportions are being compared – considering 48.0% in the intervention or experimental arm and 14.0% in the control arm, the risk difference was assumed to be 34.0%.(15) With an alpha error of 5.0%, beta error of 20.0% (or 80.0% power) we estimated the minimum required sample size to be 30 per group.

The patients were randomly allocated to the intervention and control arms using computer generated randomization sequence (blinded for the research hypothesis). Allocation concealment was done using opaque sealed envelopes kept in the operating room opened once the consent is signed. Being a surgical intervention, blinding the patients, or the surgeon, assessor, or the trial operator was not possible. Post operatively, all patients were put on a knee brace for two weeks and ambulated non weight bearing with crutches. The hip and knee joint were mobilized after the third post operative day. The patients were usually discharged on the fourth or the fifth post operative day. The sutures were removed after 7-14 days of surgery in the outpatient department. The patients were regularly followed up at two and four months of surgery and the hip/knee movements were encouraged and assessed along with the signs of radiological and clinical union.

The primary outcomes of interest were proportion of patients with malunion [assessed at the end of 24 months; defined as one or more of the following – more than 15° of angulation in the coronal plane (varus or valgus), or more than 20° of angulation in the sagittal plane (apex-anterior or apex posterior angulation), or clinically obvious malrotation (an asymmetric foot progression angle with corresponding asymmetry of internal or external rotation of the hip), or limb-length discrepancy of more than 2.0 cm]; number of serious adverse events [including non-union (remodeling (mature) callus bridging less than three of the four cortices seen on two orthogonal views of the femur), deep surgical wound infections, need for reoperation (any fracture-related procedure, other than routine hardware removal, performed after the initial fixation), nerve injuries, compartment syndrome, reduced range of movements (ROM) in proximal and distal joint as compared to the opposite side, implant related complications; and functional outcomes (using Pediatric outcomes data collection

instrument (PODCI) at the end of 6 months, 12 months and 24 months).(16, 17) The secondary outcomes of interest were time for return to routine daily activity, costs incurred, duration of surgery, amount of intra-operative blood loss, radiation exposure, time to union and duration of hospital stay.(18)

Statistical analysis: The data obtained was manually entered into Microsoft Excel, coded, and recoded. Analysis was done using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) v23. Descriptive analysis was presented using numbers and percentages for categorical variables and mean (standard deviation) or median (interquartile range) for continuous variables. Appropriate graphs were used. To test for association between independent study variables and outcomes of interest we used Chi-square test or Fisher's exact test (two sided) for categorical data and comparison of continuous data was done by using independent sample "t" test. Statistical significance was considered at $p < 0.05$.

Results

The present study included a total of 60 children 5 to 15 years of age presenting to the Department of Pediatric Orthopedics with diaphyseal fractures of femur – 30 children were treated with submuscular locked compression plating (the intervention or experimental group) and the other 30 children (the control group) were treated with elastic stable intramedullary nailing.

Baseline characteristics of the intervention and control arms: The mean (SD) age of the patients was 8.92 years (3.45). More than half (55.0%) were males. Two thirds of patients (66.7%) were presented with fracture on the right side. Road traffic accidents (RTA) were the most common (90.0%) mode of fracture. Importantly, these variables did not vary significantly between the intervention and control arms ($p > 0.05$). The results showed that majority of the patients in the intervention group had type 1 fractures (60.0%) and 70.0% patients in the control group had type 2 fractures – 86.7% patients in the intervention group had type 1 or 2 fractures; all (100%) the patients in the control group had either type 1 or 2 fractures ($p < 0.05$).

Comparing complications between the intervention and control arms: In the present study, none of the patients in either the intervention arm or the control arm developed malunion (more than 15° of angulation in the coronal plane, more than 20° of angulation in the sagittal plane, malrotation, or limb-length discrepancy > 2.0 cm) ($p > 0.05$). Regarding serious adverse events, though none of the patients in either the intervention arm or control arm developed deep surgical wound infections, or nerve injuries or compartment syndrome, there were three patients (10.0%) in the control arm (elastic stable intramedullary nailing) who had loss of reduction post-surgery due to trivial fall requiring closed reduction. However, this difference was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). The other complications including reduced range of movements and implant related complications did not vary significantly between the study groups. Five patients in the control arm (16.7%) reported joint stiffness in comparison with none of the patients in intervention arm (0.0%); however, this difference was not found to be statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

Comparing functional outcomes between the intervention and control arms: The Pediatric outcomes data collection instrument (PODCI) was used to collect the functional outcomes. A normative score of 50 was considered to be normal – scores more than 50 meant that the patient had above average functionality in that domain or overall.

The mean (SD) global function scores among patients in the intervention arm was 54.75 (1.40), significantly higher than that reported among patients in the control arm (47.75 (2.05)). The patients in the intervention arm documented higher scores in each of the four subscales – upper extremity and physical function (58.50 (1.36) vs 53.00 (2.45)), transfers and basic mobility (55.00 (1.29) vs 51.50 (1.02)), sports and physical function (49.50 (1.34) vs 41.50 (2.64)), pain and comfort (56.00 (1.62) vs 45.00 (2.10)). Except for sports and physical functioning, the overall mean scores were more than 50 in the present study.

The mean (SD) happiness and expectation scores among patients in the intervention arm was 54.50 (1.92) and 56.00 (1.23), respectively. Though the happiness scores were significantly higher among patients in the intervention arm ($p < 0.05$), no significant difference between intervention and control arms was found in terms of expectations ($p > 0.05$).

Comparing secondary outcomes between the intervention and control arms: The results of the present study showed that the duration of hospital stay (in days), time taken for union, and blood loss (in ml) did not vary significantly between the study groups ($p > 0.05$). However, the duration of radiation required was significantly

shorter among patients in the intervention arm (Median 53.00 seconds, IQR 42.00 to 61.00) in comparison with the control arm (Median 109.00 seconds, IQR 92.00 to 127.00).

Discussion

The present study aimed to compare the efficacy and outcomes of submuscular locked compression plating (intervention) and elastic stable intramedullary nailing (control) among children with diaphyseal fractures of femur. The mean age of the patients (8.92 years) falls within the age range commonly seen for pediatric diaphyseal femur fractures.(19) The male predominance (55.0%) aligns with previous studies suggesting that males are more prone to these fractures due to various factors like higher activity levels.(20) The observation that the majority of patients presented with fractures on the right side (66.7%) is interesting. While there isn't a clear consensus on side predominance in diaphyseal femur fractures, some studies have reported right-side predominance as well. The high prevalence of road traffic accidents (90.0%) as the mode of fracture is consistent with global trends, where motor vehicle accidents are a common cause of pediatric femur fractures. This finding emphasizes the need for safety measures such as child restraint systems in vehicles and pedestrian safety education.(21) The lack of significant differences in baseline characteristics between the intervention and control groups ($p > 0.05$) is reassuring, as it suggests that randomization was effective in achieving balance between the groups. This is essential to ensure that the comparison of treatment outcomes is not confounded by differences in patient characteristics. The distribution of fracture types is noteworthy. In the intervention group, the majority of patients had type 1 fractures (60.0%), while in the control group, 70.0% had type 2 fractures. These findings suggest that the fracture types were not evenly distributed between the groups. It's important to explore whether the type of fracture influenced the choice of treatment and whether this factor could have affected the study outcomes.

The results indicate that there were no cases of malunion in either the intervention or control group, based on specific criteria for angular deformity, malrotation, and limb-length discrepancy. Additionally, no deep surgical wound infections, nerve injuries, or compartment syndrome were reported in either group. However, it's noteworthy that in the control group (elastic stable intramedullary nailing), there were three cases (10.0%) of loss of reduction post-surgery due to trivial falls, which required closed reduction. While this difference was not statistically significant, it warrants discussion. It's crucial to assess the clinical impact of such events on the affected children, including any potential need for additional interventions or long-term consequences.(22)

The results indicate that there were no statistically significant differences between the study groups in terms of other complications, including reduced range of movements and implant-related complications. However, it's noteworthy that in the control group, 16.7% of patients reported joint stiffness, while none of the patients in the intervention group experienced this complication. Joint stiffness can hinder a child's ability to engage in physical activities and may require rehabilitation or other interventions. The absence of joint stiffness in the intervention group is a positive finding. The lack of statistically significant differences in implant-related complications suggests that both treatment modalities were reasonably safe with regard to implant issues. However, it's essential to consider the specific types of implant-related complications and their clinical significance. This may include issues such as irritation, prominence, or the need for implant removal.(23)

The results of the study, as assessed by the PODCI scale, reveal significant differences in functional outcomes between the intervention (submuscular locked compression plating) and control (elastic stable intramedullary nailing) arms. The higher mean global function score in the intervention arm (54.75) suggests that children who received submuscular locked compression plating had better overall functional outcomes compared to those who underwent elastic stable intramedullary nailing. Except for the "sports and physical function" subscale, all other overall mean scores were above 50. This suggests that, on average, patients in both groups achieved above-average functionality in most domains. The use of the PODCI scale was valuable for assessing and comparing functional outcomes in pediatric orthopedic patients.(24) The inclusion of normative scores allows for a clear interpretation of how patients' functional outcomes compare to the general population.(25)

Patients in the intervention arm had a mean happiness score of 54.50, which was significantly higher compared to the control arm. This finding suggests that children who received submuscular locked compression plating reported a higher level of happiness (or greater level of satisfaction and well-being) in their post-operative experience.(26) This could be attributed to various factors, such as reduced pain, improved functional outcomes, or other aspects of the treatment experience.(27) No significant difference in the duration of hospital stay was observed between the intervention and control arms. This suggests that both treatment modalities had similar impacts on the length of hospitalization for pediatric patients with diaphyseal femur fractures.(28) The time

taken for union did not significantly differ between the two study groups. This indicates that the rate of fracture healing was similar in both groups, suggesting that neither treatment modality had a distinct advantage in promoting faster union. The blood loss during surgery was comparable between the intervention and control arms. There was a significant difference in the duration of radiation required, with the intervention arm (submuscular locked compression plating) requiring a significantly shorter duration compared to the control arm (elastic stable intramedullary nailing).(29)

Conclusion

In the present study, we conducted a rigorous investigation into the efficacy and outcomes of two surgical approaches, submuscular locked compression plating (SLCP) and elastic stable intramedullary nailing (ESIN), in the management of diaphyseal femur fractures among pediatric patients. Patients in the SLCP group exhibited significantly better functional outcomes compared to those in the ESIN group. These superior outcomes encompassed various domains, including upper extremity and physical function, transfers and basic mobility, sports and physical function, as well as pain and comfort. Several clinical parameters, such as the duration of hospital stay, time taken for union, and intraoperative blood loss, were similar between the two groups, highlighting the clinical equivalence of both treatment modalities in these aspects. Notably, the SLCP group required significantly less radiation during the surgical procedure than the ESIN group. This finding suggests a potential advantage of SLCP in terms of reduced radiation exposure to patients and operating room personnel. However, further investigation is needed to explore whether fracture type had any impact on treatment outcomes, as well as any other potential confounding variables.

In summary, our study demonstrates that while both SLCP and ESIN are viable treatment options for diaphyseal femur fractures in children, SLCP appears to offer distinct advantages in terms of functional outcomes and patient happiness. Moreover, the reduced radiation exposure associated with SLCP is a notable benefit, emphasizing the importance of minimizing radiation exposure in pediatric orthopedic surgery.

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Table 1: Baseline characteristics of the intervention and control arms

		Intervention	Control	Total	P value
		N = 30	N = 30	N = 60	
Age (in years), Mean (SD)		9.12 (3.69)	8.72 (3.21)	8.92 (3.45)	0.656
Gender	Male	17 (56.7)	16 (53.3)	33 (55.0)	0.795
	Female	13 (43.3)	14 (46.7)	27 (45.0)	
Side	Right	19 (63.3)	21 (70.0)	40 (66.7)	0.584
	Left	11 (36.7)	9 (30.0)	20 (33.3)	
Mode of injury	RTA	26 (86.7)	28 (93.3)	54 (90.0)	0.389
	Fall from height	4 (13.3)	2 (6.7)	6 (10.0)	
Type of fracture	Type 1	18 (60.0)	9 (30.0)	27 (45.0)	0.005*
	Type 2	8 (26.7)	21 (70.0)	29 (48.3)	
	Type 3	4 (13.3)	0 (0.0)	4 (6.7)	
Intervention: Submuscular locked compression plating					
Control: Elastic stable intramedullary nailing					
*Statistically significant at p<0.05					
RTA, road traffic accident					

Table 2: Comparing complications between the intervention and control arms

		Intervention	Control	Total	P value
		N = 30	N = 30	N = 60	
Malunion					
>15° of angulation in the coronal plane	No	30 (100)	30 (100)	60 (100)	1.000
>20° of angulation in the sagittal plane	No	30 (100)	30 (100)	60 (100)	1.000
Malrotation	No	30 (100)	30 (100)	60 (100)	1.000
Limb-length discrepancy >2.0 cm	No	30 (100)	30 (100)	60 (100)	1.000
Serious adverse events					
Deep surgical wound infections	No	30 (100)	30 (100)	60 (100)	1.000
Need for reoperation	Yes	0 (0.0)	3 (10.0)	3 (5.0)	0.285
Nerve injuries	No	30 (100)	30 (100)	60 (100)	1.000
Compartment syndrome	No	30 (100)	30 (100)	60 (100)	1.000
Others					
Reduced ROM	No	30 (100)	30 (100)	60 (100)	1.000
Implant related complications	No	30 (100)	30 (100)	60 (100)	1.000
Joint stiffness	Yes	0 (0.0)	5 (16.7)	5 (8.3)	0.078
*Statistically significant at p<0.05 ROM, range of movements					

Table 3: Comparing functional outcomes between the intervention and control arms

	Intervention	Control	Total	P value
	N = 30	N = 30	N = 60	
Global function	54.75 (1.40)	47.75 (2.05)	51.25 (1.73)	<0.001*
Upper extremity and physical function	58.50 (1.36)	53.00 (2.45)	55.75 (1.91)	<0.001*
Transfers and basic mobility	55.00 (1.29)	51.50 (1.02)	53.25 (1.16)	<0.001*
Sports and physical function	49.50 (1.34)	41.50 (2.64)	45.5 (1.99)	<0.001*
Pain and comfort	56.00 (1.62)	45.00 (2.10)	50.5 (1.86)	<0.001*
Happiness	54.50 (1.92)	53.00 (2.38)	53.75 (2.15)	0.009*
Expectations	56.00 (1.23)	55.50 (2.38)	55.75 (1.81)	0.311
*Statistically significant at p<0.05				

Table 4: Comparing secondary outcomes between the intervention and control arms

Variables	Type of measure	Intervention	Control	P value
		N = 30	N = 30	
Duration of hospital stay (in days)	Median (IQR)	5.00 (4.00 to 6.00)	4.00 (3.00 to 5.00)	0.482
Time taken for union	Median (IQR)	11.50 (9.50 to 12.00)	10.00 (9.50 to 16.50)	0.385
Blood loss in ml	Mean (SD)	105.79 (74.63)	86.69 (36.82)	0.082
Duration of radiation (in seconds)	Median (IQR)	53.00 (42.00 to 61.00)	109.00 (92.00 to 127.00)	<0.001*
*Statistically significant at p<0.05 SD, Standard deviation; IQR, interquartile range				